

Demographic Differentials in the Use of Information and Communication Technologies among Lecturers in Colleges of Education in Ondo State

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Abstract

This study investigated into demographic differentials in the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) among lecturers in colleges of education in Ondo state. The study investigated the differences that exist between the gender, lecturer's qualification(s) and age of lecturers and the use of ICTs. The objectives of the study were to: (i) to determine the difference in ICTs usage between male and female Colleges of Education (COE) lecturers. (ii) to investigate the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) (iii) Find out the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age. The study was conducted using a descriptive method. The title of the questionnaire used to collect data is "Demographic Differentials of ICTs usage among COE Lecturers" (DDIACL). Three (3) research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two hundred (200) respondents were sampled using simple random technique. The instrument for data collection was researcher's designed questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale items. Five (5) experts in the field of Educational Technology validated the instrument to ensure content and face validity of the instrument. The reliability of the constructs was examined using the Cronbach's Alpha and it yielded 0.78 value. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA from the results analyzed. It was revealed from the study that COE lecturers' gender, academic qualification(s) and age has no significance difference in the use of ICTs. The study concluded that lecturers in COE have been using ICTs for teaching, research and management regardless of their gender, academic qualification(s) and age. It was therefore recommended that lecturers in COE should actively participates in ICTs training and by putting favourable attitudes towards technology.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), College of Education, Lecturers' Demography

Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are defined as all devices, tools, contents, resources, forums, and services, digital and those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forms, which can be deployed for realizing the goals of teaching and learning, enhancing access to and reach of resources, building of capacities, as well as management of the educational system. (Abba & Adamu, 2019). These will not only include hardware devices connected to computers and software applications but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums, learning management systems, and management informant in systems. These will also include processes for digitization, deployment and management of platforms and processes for capacity development and creation of forums for interaction and exchange. (Abba & Adam, 2019).

The College of Education is a unit of tertiary education in Nigeria saddled with the responsibility of training teachers to obtain qualitative professional certification in education. The philosophy underpinning teacher education at the College of Education as opined by Isiyaku (2007), included the desire of the Nigerian Government to ensure uniformity of the content and educational standard. It also aimed at producing teachers with highly personal and professional discipline and integrity, teachers who are dedicated and with appropriate skills and intellectual depth that would facilitate easy achievement of the national goal. This is more critical when we note government's decision that the NCE shall ultimately be the minimum entry qualification into the teaching profession in Nigeria. Lecturers in the colleges of education are required to integrate Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) into their classroom activities. ICTs proficiency is the ability of lecturer to use ICTs

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appropriately to access, manage, integrate, and evaluate information, develop new understanding, and communicates with others in order to participate effectively in the society (Ministerial Council on Education, Development, and Youth Affairs, (MCEECD)2008).

It was opined by Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD (2014) that majority of teachers choose to develop their ICTs related skills during their own spare time which may include various means of professional development such as training provided by school staff and participation in online communities. Teachers' age, gender and qualification(s) are factors associated with ICTs use. ICTs skills, age, gender and qualification(s) in combination, are accepted precursors for effective use of ICTs (Migliorino & Maiden, 2004) Therefore, there is need to determine the ICTs usage amongst lecturers in Colleges of Education, (COE) in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are now used in various educational aspects for enriching the quality of teaching and learning. The availability of ICTs tools in higher institutions has proven to enhance teaching and learning; enabled self-paced learning; removed the time and space barriers for learning. (Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Adogbeji, 2013). Also, studies have shown that students' learning and teachers' teaching are enhanced when ICTs are used efficiently and effectively (Apagu & Wakili, 2015). Gender comparisons are needed to give a better understanding of lecturers' use of ICTs. Recently ICTs is gradually replacing the traditional teacher-centered teaching and learning environment in education and emphasis has shifted from the teacher to the learner, this becomes pertinent that both male and female teachers adopt the use of ICTs in facilitating learning (Fomsi & Orduah, 2017).

A study carried out by Hallberg et.al., (2011) found out that male lecturers used ICT facilities mostly as compared to the female counterpart. Similarly, Tezci (2009) found significant influence of gender on the level of utilization of ICT facilities by teachers. Also, Agbatogun (2013) did not find any significant influence of gender on lecturers' use of ICT facilities. Not only that Sherman (2013) mentioned that although the majority of internet users was narrowing down. Heimrath and Goulding (2001) found that female students felt that the internet was too big and unstructured thus, searching the internet difficult not enjoyable and would use it only they have to whereas male students were happy to search the internet for relevant information.

In a study by Usun (2003) on the use of ICTs by male and female students. It was found that there is no gender difference in access to the internet. It was found that male spend more time on computers and surfing the internet than female counterparts and it was reported that male students spent on average 5 to 10 hours per week, while female students reported that they spent less than 5 hours average per week (Mahmood & Bokhari, 2012). Sandra and Kurfi (2013) also reiterated that despite the much emphasis placed on the use of ICTs in Nigeria, women are usually underrepresented in terms of access and use of ICTs. They also observed that though women play a pivotal role in the development of their societies, yet their impact has been silenced in this new technology due to lack of access and the necessary skills for the operation. Mahmood and Bokhari (2012) opined that gender equity persists both in access to and experience of learning opportunities with ICT. Shashaani and Khalili (2001) in their study revealed that there is pervasive difference between the ways females and males use technology to socialize. The survey demonstrated that there is a strong gender gap in the way respondents make friend online. Girls are more likely to participate in social networks, create blogs, use instant messaging, use e-mail, and post pictures, keep tabs on family and communicate with one another, and share and research on how to obtain information. In contrast boys are more likely than girls to post online video content. Sherman (2013) opined that girls often place more calls, text more, and generally use social/communicative apps and sites more than boys which reflect broader gender differences in communication beyond just that occur in a technology.

Another factor that was found to play a vital role in the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in teaching by lecturers in Colleges of Nigeria is the lecturers' academic qualifications. It was found out by Odigwe and Owau (2020) that there is a significant influence of staff educational qualification on the utilization of ICTs resources for teaching, research and records management in higher educational and qualifications are not good users of ICTs facilities, reason for this to the researchers is that to attain a higher educational qualification, age has a critical role to play. In their research age and rank may have been the reason responsible for this finding. On the contrary, Gombe et.al (2016) found no significant difference in the utilization of ICT based on lecturers' qualification. Onasanya et al., (2010) in their research on higher institutions lecturers' attitude towards integration of ICT into teaching and research in Nigeria was found that the less experience lecturers are more than their senior colleagues.

Also, in a research study carried out by Lubis et.al., (2017), it was found out that years of teaching experiences and educational level of academic staff have no significant influence on the utilization of the technology. However, Herath and Hewagama (2015) stated that teaching experiences is not significantly affecting the ICT usage. The result pointed out that the different teaching experience is not in line with the utilization of ICT. In Nigerian Colleges of Education, lecturers are

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divided into four (4) levels, which are Higher National Diploma (HND) First degree level, master's level and doctoral level (PHD). Morley (2010) confirmed there is a significant different between educational level and teachers using ICT. The higher educational level of lecturers is more frequently to utilize ICT.

Many scholars have been drawn to examine the influence of age on the usage of ICTs in higher education. (Lubis et al., 2017). Albion, et al. (2011) held that age is significant predictor of lecturers' usage of ICTs in higher institutions of learning. Etim (2019) & Alba & Trani, 2018; Amua-sekyi & Asare, 2016) held to the contrary that age does not significantly predict ICTs usage. Odigwe et al., (2020) found out in their research study that younger lecturers demonstrated higher utility of ICT resources in higher education than older lecturers. This finding is unsurprising since younger lecturers are less busy with administrative responsibilities and may have little or no family responsibility to meet compared with older lecturers. Dei (2018) opinion that ICTs purely obeys the law of diminishing returns and posited that the usage of ICTs depreciates as an individual grow older. Manyilizu and Gilbert (2015) indicated that age is a barrier and has no effect on the use of ICTs. It is believed that young people are more curious Jegede (2009) conducted a study that age was not found to affect the time used on ICTs by higher education teachers in Nigeria

The focus of previous studies was on lecturers' attitude towards the use of ICTs in Nigeria. Very few studies have examined the effect of gender, academic qualification(s) and age on the use of ICTs in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also, most of these studies were conducted in developing countries where technology was in its high position. The situation may be different if studies are conducted in developing countries or where technology usage is still in its primitive stages. The teachers in these situations face different difficulties that may impede the use of ICTs in teaching and learning in schools. Therefore, the present study explores lecturers related factors that may affect the usage of ICTs in teaching and learning in Colleges of Education (COE) in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To assess the difference in ICTs usage between male and female COE lecturers in Ondo State.
2. To assess the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) in Ondo state.
3. To examine the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age in Ondo state.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage between male and female COE lecturers in Ondo State.
2. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) in Ondo state.
3. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age in Ondo state

Methodology

The study was a descriptive research type. The population for the study was lecturers in Colleges of Education in Ondo state Nigeria and the total number of lecturers are four hundred and forty. The targeted population of this research consisted of lecturers in Colleges of Education in three Colleges namely: Adeyemi College of Education Ondo, Ondo State is having the total population of three hundred and eighty-nine (389), All State College of Education, Ero is having twenty (20) lecturers and Bethel College of Education, Ijare is having thirty (30) lecturers all in Ondo State. The overall total of lecturers regardless of the of school and gender are four hundred and forty nine (449). In all, a total of (200) two hundred lecturers were selected using simple random technique and they responded to the instrument and data collected was finally processed. The dependent variable of concern was the Colleges of Education lecturers' usage of ICT. Intervening variables of gender, academic qualification(s) and age of lecturers were considered.

The instrument for data collection used for the study was a questionnaire, developed by researcher and titled of the questionnaire is 'Demographic Differentials of ICTs usage among COE lecturers' (DFICCEL). The questionnaire had two sections A and B. Section A was concerned with demographic information while section B sought to know how Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) can be effectively used by Colleges of Education (COE) in Ondo state, Nigeria. The researcher administered copies of questionnaire within four (4) weeks by visiting the Colleges with the help of research assistant in various Colleges. At the end of the exercise two hundred (200) valid copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, upon which analysis of the results was carried. Mean, standard deviation, t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data collected.

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Five experts from departments of Educational Technology from Department of Educational Technology from University of Ilorin, Ilorin validated the instrument. The experts assessed the appropriateness and adequacy of the content of the instrument. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument a pilot study was conducted among COE lecturers from two Colleges of Education in Ogun state not part of the main sample. The two (2) results of administration were compared using Cronbach's Alpha co-efficient and the co-efficient of internal consistency was 0.78.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in ICT usage between male and female colleges of education lecturers using ICTs in Ondo state.

Table 1: Summary of t-test Showing Difference Between Male and Female Lecturers' ICT Usage in Colleges of Education

Grouping Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	Sig.	Remark
Male	80	23.50	2.25	198	.159	.874	Not Significant
Female	120	23.45	2.14				

Table 1 shows the difference in the usage of ICT by male and female lecturers in colleges of education in Ondo state. The table shows that the mean score for male lecturers is 23.50 while that of female lecturers' usage is 23.45. The values of the mean scores do not reveal an appreciable difference. Therefore, there is no significant difference in ICT usage between male and female colleges of education lecturers in Ondo state ($df = 198$; $t = .159$; $p > 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 1 is retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied academic qualifications in Ondo state.

Table 2: Summary of ANOVA Showing Difference in Lecturers' Usage of ICT based on Academic Qualification

Qualifications	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
HND	33	22.18	1.91
First Degree	55	24.15	1.89
Master's Degree	65	23.39	2.28
PhD	47	23.70	2.17
Total	200	23.47	2.18

Analysis of Variance						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	82.860	3	27.620	6.288	.000	Significant
Within Groups	860.960	196	4.393			
Total	943.820	199				

Table 2 shows the difference in lecturers' usage of ICT based on their academic qualification. The table shows that the mean score for lecturers with HND is 22.18, those with first degree is 24.15, those with master's degree is 23.38 while that of lecturers with Ph.D is 23.70. The ANOVA results shows that there is significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied academic qualifications in Ondo state ($F_{(3,196)} = 6.288$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied age in Ondo state.

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Table 3: Summary of ANOVA Showing Difference in Lecturers' Usage of ICT in College of Education based on Age

Age Range	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
20-25years	6	23.17	.98
26-30years	28	23.93	2.07
31-36years	36	22.89	2.41
37-40years	50	23.84	1.98
41years and Above	80	23.36	2.25
Total	200	23.47	2.18

Analysis of Variance						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	26.366	4	6.592			
Within Groups	917.454	195	4.705	1.401	.235	Not Significant
Total	943.820	199				

Table 4 shows the difference in the lecturers of colleges of education students' usage of ICTs based on their age range. The table shows that the mean score for lecturers between ages of 20 to 25years is 23.17, those between 26 to 30years is 23.93, those between 31 to 36years is 22.89, those between 37 to 40years is 23.84 while that of lecturers aged 41years and above is 23.36. The ANOVA results shows that there is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied age in Ondo state ($F_{(4,195)} = 1.401$; $p > 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 3 is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Result on influence of gender on lecturers' usage of ICTs facilities for teaching purpose showed that there was no statistically significant difference between male and female lecturers on the use of ICT facilities for teaching purpose. The study agrees with previous findings (Fomsi & Orduah, 2017, Tezci, 2009, Halberg et al., 2011, Usun 2013, Mahmood and Bohkam, 2012, Sanda and Kirfi, 2013), it is in the contrast to Heimrath and Goulding 2001 which found a significant difference between the male and female lecturers in using ICTs in teaching and other purposes. Also, Shashaani and Khalili, (2001) in their study revealed that is pervasive difference between the ways females and males use technology to socialize. The result from this investigation also shows the lecturers with PHD and master's qualification had slightly higher mean ratings on level of usage of ICTs in teaching than those with HND and first degree. This result is not surprising because the added qualification of the lecturers must have exposed them to various skills of using ICTs. The ANOVA result showed that there was no significant different between lecturers' level of using ICTs based on qualification. The result agrees with the findings of Odigwe and Owan (2020) that there was a significant influence of staff educational qualification on the utilization of ICTs resources for teaching, research and records management in higher education on the contrary, Gombe et al. (2016) found no significant difference in the utilization of ICTs based on lecturers' qualification.

The result in table three showed the age of lecturers as it influences the use of ICTs among the lecturers of Colleges of Education in Ondo state. The ANOVA indicated that the age of the lecturers does not have significant relationship with the use of ICTs among lecturers. This agrees with Lubis et al., (2017) and Herath and Hewagamase (2015) that teaching experiences is not significantly affecting the ICTs usage. On the contrary, Morley (2010) confirmed that there is a significant different between educational level and teachers using ICTs. The higher educational level of lecturers is more frequently to utilize ICTs.

Conclusion

This study investigated the demographic differentials of lecturers in Colleges of Education (COEs) usage of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in Ondo state, Nigeria. This study has showed that ICTs were extensively used by lecturers regardless of their gender, qualification(s) and age. It was revealed that both male and female lecturers adequately utilise ICTs for different purposes such as teaching, research, computation of results and management in general. Hence, it can be concluded that factors such as gender, academic qualification(s) and age does not hinder the use of ICTs among lecturers of Colleges of Education in Ondo state.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Training should be given to both male and female lecturers to enable them effectively use ICTs for research, teaching and for management.
2. Regardless of lecturers age, all lecturers in colleges of education should be ICT compliance in using it to perform different activities.
3. Lecturers across different education, qualification(s) should make conscious efforts to avail themselves of the opportunity of becoming ICT literates through active participation in ICT retraining and by putting forth favourable attitude towards technology

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